

Viable Monitoring Management System for Higher Education

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ABSTRACT

This research aimed to develop an Admission Monitoring Management System and its acceptability and sustainability at Informatics College Cebu Region VII during School Year 2017-2018 towards technology sustainability. It employed descriptive-correlation method with the use of survey questionnaire as the primary means of gathering the data. The statistical treatments used were the simple percentage, weighted mean, and the concordance agreement. A total of 31 respondents in different three (3) areas were considered in the study. As revealed in the technology user's information, based on the gender representation majority of personnel is dominated by Female when it comes to the work force

and the majority respondents at the age bracket of 30 yrs. old to 40yrs and this implies that among the characteristics attributed to Xers life. Acceptability of Admission Monitoring Management system shows that the administrators, managers and system operators in the three areas have high positive perception on usefulness and ease of use, high positive attitude and behavioral intention in using the system. Based on the result of the Admission Monitoring Management System for Informatics College Region VII in terms of Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Attitude Towards Using and Behavioral Intention to Use the Technology Management Program should be given immediate attention and action by the college. The Admission Monitoring Management System as the degree of functionality was evaluated and rated Well Developed as to; Administrator Module, Managers Module and System Operators Module. The Admission Monitoring Management System as the degree of acceptability was evaluated and rated Strongly Agree as to; Administrator: Technical Personnel, Service Officers, Managers: Center Manager, Academics Head and System Operators: Cashier, Course Consultant and Registrar.

Keywords: *Information Management System Evaluation, Technology Sustainability, Technology Acceptability, Perceived Usefulness and Technology Acceptance Model*

INTRODUCTION

As technology continues to advance, computers become a closer to everyday life. Computers are already seen everywhere at work, at school, and at home. Daily activities either involve the use of or depend on information from a computer. This may be because computers are used in almost every field and profession, like education and office works to perform a large number of computer related work. Computerization is a control system that manages processes in the industrial workplace. It reduces human errors and processing time thus it can boost productivity that results in high quality of product. In

information system, computerization is concerned about interrelating different but interdependent transactions. This can result in a system with well-integrated processes that can perform much faster and more accurate than a manual or semi-automated system. In the field of education, researchers and theorists have focused intensively in recent years on examining the concepts and use of information to assist Course Consultants, Cashier, Registrar, Academics Head, Service Officer, Technical personnel and Administrator. Schools, like any other organization used to overmanage all sorts of data and information to ensure attainment of its goals and objectives. The emerging needs in most schools for accurate and relevant data and reliable information strengthen the student information.

A pre-survey were conducted by the researcher at Informatics College and records of complaint that leads to the Registrar's issuance of an NTE (notice to explain) since the registrar creates her own Spreadsheet data recording just to facilitate faster transaction during the admission process, though it is an Information & Communication Technology School which is capable of producing a computerized system still where to utilize the use of a seminal manual process in recording and retrieving student's information. The target responder of the study has a separate office and with an individual computer; The Course Consultants, Cashier, Registrar, Service Officer, Technical personnel and the school Administrator have experience setbacks of the current system in admitting the students. The lack of manpower to accommodate all enrollees, Course Consultants has a lot of forms to be confirmed that is being filled up by the students since the students every admission will fill-up tedious of forms. And tedious task of filling out the application form and the inaccuracies of information provided by the students. As a result, it may cause admission delays due to students' laziness in filling-up the forms. Cashier has to input again student information in another file because some records does not coincide with the registrar data/records because of not having an integrated system. Registrar's office also used a manual system as a way of recording and retrieving student information and delayed/un-updated master list and printing of study loads and delayed in the release of study loads due to errors in updating/changing of subjects coming from the registrar's office. Some of the impediments also experienced in the Semi Manual Admission System; Data was constantly being duplicated. This was time-consuming and resources were being wasted, some of the data entered were redundant as there was no repetition check as with a computer, The office space had to be increased as more space was needed to store filing cabinets as the amount of paper increased, Lack of security as data was stored in filing cabinets. Without the knowledge of the School Administrator and Registrar, unauthorized users may have had access to confidential information, Data was only being accessed by one employee at a time. This was time-consuming. Hence, this led to the school of being unproductive, Data was constantly being misplaced. This jeopardized the business future of Informatics College, and Risk of data being destroyed due to natural disasters, age, etc. All of the setback and impediments experienced by each of the respondents in the Semi Manual Admission System has been a perineal problem by Informatics College ever since and it must be corrected. The researcher's observation, human interventions will highly involve in this type of system. As a result, this may involve errors and duplication of data resulting troubles in organization. Informatics Manila ones introduce a readymade software Schoolista, an "*online*" school system designed to support small and medium schools through the computerization of school operations. But before they integrate to other branches serious of debates and discussion has been raised because Schoolista did not answer some specific problems encountered by Informatics specifically the school admission management process.

According to Forman (2007), in his article "New Research Perspectives on Mobility, Organizations, Systems and Technologies," continuing innovation in technologies can lead to organizational changes that range from improvement of day-to-day operation and for easy access it provides for the end users. Many schools today have adapted this innovation in the offering of their services. The Admission Monitoring Management System allows a management process, eliminating or reducing problems with traditional

registration systems, such as long lines, paper forms and troublesome wait lists Admission Monitoring Management System is very essential in a school. As a result, inspired by the computerized registration services, the researcher came up with a customized ADMISSION MONITORING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM OF INFORMATICS COLLEGE, REGION VII. The study considered the prevailing process of the school (Informatics College, Region VII) and this process can be modified to have a more efficient and effective admission monitoring system. Switching to a computerized Admission Monitoring Management System is an obvious next step to bridge the gap between manual methods and computerized admission management systems. The amount of errors and problems that can be saved is enough to make a difference in our education system. A computerized Admission Monitoring Management System is a management information systems that can answer the gap between the semi-manual Admission Monitoring Management system to the computerized Admission Monitoring Management System in general such as: Duplication of data will be reduced as record keeping will be done more efficiently, as adding, deleting and updating information will reduce the use of stationary- by reducing cost- as well as be less time-consuming. This will lead Informatics College to become more productive as employees could perform additional tasks, Data entered will not be redundant as the Information System will utilize the “Repetition”, Overheads will be drastically reduced. This will result in a reduction of office space and equipment. This will maximize Informatics College profits, the data entered will be confidential and secure, via the use of passwords, Data could be accessed by multiple employees at a time. This will lead to Informatics College becoming more productive, Data was not misplaced as it will be held in ‘fixed’ storage locations, Employees will have an easy, rapid, efficient way of finding and retrieving data, Data will have ‘backups’ in case of natural disasters. This means that all business information will not be permanently destroyed. Hence, Informatics College data/files could have a starting point to resume records retrieval, As Informatics College grows, the Information System will evolve and adapt as well. The use of Information Technology will also aid in effective decision-making. The researcher is strong-minded that Informatics College is capable of accepting and adopting a new admission system since; the users of the system are computer literate and knowledgeable in fixing minor computer problems. The research environment is capable of acquiring the new system hence they are fully equipped to implementing the new Admission Monitoring Management System. Determining user acceptance of a system is a difficult but important part of human factors research and application. While there is currently no complete theory or model that explains and predicts acceptance, there is an emerging understanding of the key variables in the technology, the user and the implementation process that affect acceptability. To be accepted, a technology must satisfy basic usability requirements and be perceived as useful by its intended user community. User experience and training will impact acceptance levels as will the manner in which the technology is implemented to contribute to organizational goals and working practices.

The Researcher want to validate Admission Monitoring Management System to be used by Informatics College, Region VII will perceive useful to its intended users. At least part of this concern is based around the issue of whether any information technology is accepted by its intended users. Human factors professionals are interested in understanding the determinants of acceptance and ensuring new designs are built and implemented so as to minimize resistance. This concern has extended the traditional ergonomic concern with usability, or ability to use, to cover acceptance, or willingness to use.

Theoretical Background

In order to validate the Admission Monitoring Management System of Informatics College Region VII that will improve the current state of Informatics College Region VII, the researcher selected the following backgrounds. Hence, wide-ranging theoretical frameworks were used to analyze the individual’s acceptance of technologies. According to Hoenig (1995) as well as Lai (2016) noted that the rate at which

payment systems develop depends largely on a struggle between rapid technological change and natural barriers to new product or service acceptance. A number of theories have proposed to explain consumers' acceptance of new technologies and their intention to use. These included, but were not restricted to, the Theory of Diffusion of Innovations (DIT) (Rogers, 2003) that started in 1960, technology Readiness (TR) (Parasuraman and Colby, 2001), the Theory of Task- technology fit (TTF) (Goodhue, and Thompson, 1995), the Theory of Reasonable Action (TRA) (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975), Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) (Ajzen, 1985, 1991), Decomposed Theory of Planned Behaviour, (Taylor and Todd, 1995), the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) (Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw, 1989), Final version of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) Venkatesh and Davis (1996), Technology Acceptance Model 2 (TAM2) Venkatesh and Davis (2000), Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT), Venkatesh, Morris, Davis and Davis (2003) and Technology Acceptance Model 3 (TAM3) Venkatesh and Bala (2008).

Rogers (1995) proposed that the theory of ‘diffusion of innovation’ was to establish the foundation for conducting research on innovation acceptance and adoption. Rogers synthesized research from over 508 diffusion studies and came out with the ‘diffusion of innovation’ theory for the adoption of innovations among individuals and organization. The theory explicates “the process by which an innovation is communicated through certain channels over time among the members of a social system” (Rogers, 1995, p. 5). In this renowned 5th edition theory, Everett M. Rogers (2003), professor and chair of the Department of Communication & Journalism at the University of New Mexico, explains how new ideas spread via communication channels over time. Such innovations are initially perceived as uncertain and even risky. To overcome this uncertainty, most people seek out others like themselves who have already adopted the new idea. Thus, the diffusion process consists of a few individuals who first adopt an innovation, then spread the word among their circle of acquaintances—a process which typically takes months or years. But there are exceptions: use of the Internet in the 1990s, for example, may have spread more rapidly than any other innovation in the history of humankind. Furthermore, the Internet is changing the very nature of

diffusion by decreasing the importance of physical distance between people. The fifth edition addresses the spread of the Internet, and how it has transformed the way human beings communicate and adopt new ideas.

Technology Readiness (TR) refers to people's propensity to embrace and use of new technologies for accomplishing goals in home life and at work (Parasuraman and Colby, 2001). Based on individual's technology readiness score and the technology readiness, Parasuraman and Colby (2001) further classified technology consumers into five technology readiness segments of explorers, pioneers, skeptics, paranoids, and laggards. This is similar to Rogers (1995) S-shaped adoption curve of innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority and laggards. The Diffusion of innovation or Technology readiness is vital for organization implementation success because it is market focus. According to Goodhue et al. (1995), Task-technology Fit (TTF) emphasizes individual impact. Individual impact refers to improved efficiency, effectiveness, and/or higher quality. Goodhue et al. (1995) assumed that the good fit between task and technology is to increase the likelihood of utilization and also to increase the performance impact since the technology meets the task needs and wants of users more closely. This model is suitable for investigating the actual usage of the technology especially testing of new technology to get feedback. The task-technology fit is good for measuring the technology applications already release in the marketplace like in the google play store or apple store app (iTunes) etc.

The Theory of Reasonable Action (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1980) is one of the most popular theories used and is about one factor that determines behavioral intention of the person's attitudes toward that behaviour. Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) defined "attitude" as the individual's evaluation of an object and defined "belief" as a link between an object and some attribute and defined "behaviour" as a result or intention. Attitudes are affective and based upon a set of beliefs about the object of behaviour (for example: Credit card is convenient). A second factor is the person's subjective norms of what they perceive their immediate community's attitude to certain behaviour (for example: my peers are using credit card and it's a status to have one). Ajzen (1991) developed Theory of Planned Behavior which is about one factor that determines behavioural intention of the person's attitudes toward that behaviour. The first two factors are the same as Theory of Reasonable Action (Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975). The third factor that is known as the perceived control behaviour is the control which users perceive that may limit their behavior (e.g: Can I apply for the credit card and what are the requirements?).

Decomposed Theory of Planned Behavior (Decomposed TPB) was introduced by Taylor and Todd (1995). The Decomposed TPB consists of three main factors influencing behavior intention and actual behavior adoption which are attitude, subjective norms and perceived behavior control. Shih and Fang (2004) examined the adoption of internet banking by means of the TPB as well as Decomposed TPB. There has been a great deal of research on the Theory of Reasoned Action (Ajzen & Fishbein, 1980; Sheppard, Hartwick, and Warshaw, 1988) A Comparison of the Theory of Planned Behavior and the Theory of Reasoned Action (Thomas J. Madden, Pamela Scholder Ellen, Icek Ajzen, 1992) and Decomposed Theory of Planned Behaviour, (Taylor and Todd, 1995) but mostly used for products already in the marketplace and included the view of society (Subjective norm). Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) was introduced by Fred Davis in 1986 for his doctorate proposal. An adoption of Theory of Reasonable Action, TAM is specifically tailored for modeling users' acceptance of information systems or technologies. Davis used TAM (Technology Acceptance Model) to explain computer usage behavior. The goal of Davis' (1989) TAM is to explain the general determinants of computer acceptance that lead to explaining users' behaviour across a broad range of end-user computing technologies and user populations. The basic TAM model included and tested two specific beliefs: Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEU). Perceived Usefulness is defined as the potential user's subjective likelihood that the use of a certain system (e.g: single platform Admission Monitoring Management System) will improve his/her action and Perceived Ease of Use refers to the degree to which the potential user expects the target system to be effortless (Davis, 1989).

The belief of the person towards a system may be influenced by other factors referred to as external variables in TAM. The final version of Technology Acceptance Model was formed by Venkatesh and Davis (1996) after the main finding of both perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use were found to have a direct influence on behaviour intention, thus eliminating the need for the attitude construct.

Venkatesh and Davis (2000) proposed the Technology Acceptance Model. This study provided more detail explanations for the reasons users found a given system useful at three (3) points in time: pre-implementation, one-month post-implementation and three-month post implementation. Technology Acceptance Model 2 theorizes that users' mental assessment of the match between important goals at work and the consequences of performing job tasks using the system serves as a basis for forming perceptions regarding the usefulness of the system (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000). The results revealed that Technology Acceptance Model 2 performed well in both voluntary and mandatory environment.

Venkatesh and Bala (2008) combined Technology Acceptance Model 2 (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000) and the model of the determinants of perceived ease of use (Venkatesh, 2000), and developed an integrated model of technology acceptance known as Technology Acceptance Model 3. The authors developed the TAM3 using the four different types including the individual differences, system characteristics, social influence, and facilitating conditions which are determinants of perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use. In Technology Acceptance Model 3 research model, the perceived ease of use to perceived usefulness, computer anxiety to perceived ease of use and perceived ease of use to behavioral intention were moderated by experiences. The Technology Acceptance Model 3 research model was tested in real-world settings of IT implementations.

Venkatesh, Morris, Davis and Davis (2003) studied from the previous models/theories and formed Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). The UTAUT has four predictors of users' behavioral intention and there are performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence and facilitating conditions. The five similar constructs including perceived usefulness, extrinsic motivation, job-fit, relative advantage and outcome expectations form the performance expectancy in the UTAUT model while effort expectancy captures the notions of perceived ease of use and complexity. As for the social context, Venkatesh et al. (2003) validation tests found that social influence was not significant in voluntary contexts.

Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw's (1989) study compared the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) with Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) and resulted in the convergence of TAM and TRA. This led to a model based on the three theoretical determinants which are the perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and behaviour intention. The study found social norms (SN) as an important determinant of behavior intention to be weak. TAM does not include social norms (SN) as a determinant of behavior intention (BI), which is an important determinant, theorized by Theory of Reasoned Action TRA and Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB).

Mathieson (1991) and Yi, Jackson, Park, and Probst (2006) argued that human and social factors could play a role in the adoption of technology using TPB model. Therefore, the TAM could be extended with constructs from the TPB to incorporate the social factors that could explain technology adoption. Nevertheless, the TPB in Chau and Hu (2002) noted that social norm and behavior intention to use finding was negative and did not support that social norm would influence behavior intention. Shih and Fang (2004) also examined the adoption of internet banking by means of the TPB as well as Decomposed TPB and found that it was in line with the findings of Venkatesh and Davis (2000) that subjective norm was likely to have a significant influence on behavioural intention to use in a mandatory environment, whilst the effect could be insignificant in a voluntary environment. Since, this study is voluntary; Therefore, the Shih and Fang (2004) study will not apply in the novel technology of single platform E-payment System.

Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw (1989) explained that social norms scales had a very poor psychometric standpoint and might not exert any influence on consumers' behavior intention, especially when the information system application like single platform System was fairly personal while individual usage was voluntary. TAM was also specifically designed to address the factors of users' system technology acceptance (Chau and Hu 2002). Thus, the comparisons of the study confirmed that Technology Acceptance Model was easy to apply across different research settings.

Han (2003) as well as Lai and Zainal (2014; 2015) noted that using TAM capability was favorable compared with TRA and TPB. TAM2, an extension of the TAM was developed by Venkatesh and Davis (2000) due to the limitations of the TAM in terms of explanatory power (R^2). The aspiration for the TAM2 was to keep the original TAM constructs intact and "include additional key determinants of TAM's perceived usefulness and usage intention constructs, and to understand how the effect of these determinants changed with increasing users' experience over time with the target system" (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000). Because TAM2 only focused on the determinants of TAM's perceived usefulness and usage intention constructs, TAM3 by Venkatesh and Bala (2008) added the determinants of TAM's perceived ease of use and usage intention constructs for robustness. Therefore, TAM3 presented a complete nomological network of the determinants of users' Information Technology System adoption (Venkatesh and Bala, 2008).

Venkatesh et al. (2003) incorporated four key determinants in the UTAUT model and there were performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence and facilitation conditions as well as four key moderators like gender, age, voluntariness and experience. According to Bagozzi (2007), UTAUT might be a powerful model due to its parsimonious structure and higher explanatory power (R^2) but the model did not examine direct effects which might reveal new relationships as well as important factors from the study which were left out by subsuming under the existing predictors only. Technology Acceptance Model 2 and Technology Acceptance Model 3 also did not measure and examine direct effects which might reveal new relationships as well as important factors from the study Technology Acceptance Model (TAM2) by Venkatesh and Davis (2000), TAM3 by Venkatesh and Bala (2008) and UTAUT by Venkatesh, Morris, Davis and Davis (2003) were not selected since the situation was for products to be implemented in the marketplace and taken into consideration of subjective norm that included society not required for this study involving the novelty technology of single platform E-payment System. Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw (1989) explained that social norms scales had a very poor psychometric standpoint and might not exert any influence on consumers' behavior intention, especially when information system application like single platform E-payment System was fairly personal while individual usage was voluntary. UTAUT is an extension from TAM2 and TAM3 is an extension of TAM2 that includes social influence, therefore they will not be used in this study based on social norm. TAM2, TAM3 and UTAUT use moderators but the present study only focuses on the factors and consumers' intention to use single platform E-payment System. Furthermore, TAM2, TAM3 and UTAUT did not include direct relations studies. Therefore, TAM2, TAM3 and UTAUT were not favorable to study the novelty technology of single platform E-payment System.

TAM model developed by Davis is the most used framework in predicting information technology adoption (Paul, John and Pierre, 2003). Lee and Jun (2007) argued that TAM should be able to analyze factors affecting adoption intentions beyond perceptions of convenience and usefulness. Though TAM had received much support (Yang, 2005), it focused on the effects of perceptions of the technology's usefulness and convenience on adoption intentions (Luarn and Lin, 2005; Lai and Zainal, 2015). Thus, it is favorable for the use of determining the novelty technology like the single platform E-payment System. In fact, TAM has become so popular that it has been cited in most of the research that deals with users' acceptance of technology (Lee, Kozar and Larsen, 2013). TAM attempts to help researchers and practitioners to distinguish why a particular technology or system may be acceptable or unacceptable and

take up suitable measures by explanation besides providing prediction. Even though TAM has been tested widely with different samples in different situations and proved to be valid and reliable model explaining information system acceptance and use (Mathieson, 1991; Davis and Venkatesh, 1996.), many extensions to the TAM have been proposed and tested (e.g. Venkatesh and Davis, 2000; Venkatesh, Speier and Morris 2002; Henderson and Divett, 2003; Lu, Yu, Liu, and Yao, 2003; Lai and Zainal, 2014; 2015; Lai, 2016). It was mentioned by Davis that behavior intention to use was being mediated by attitude. Nevertheless, attitude was excluded as its mediator in Venkatesh and Davis (2000) TAM2 and theorized a direct relationship between the constructs and intention to use. TAM initially included attitude, but this was later dropped due to its weak role as a mediator between the constructs and intention to use (Mun, Joyce, Jae & Janice, 2006).

Alice H. Eagly (2007), Research has established a mixed picture for contemporary female leadership. Women leaders on average manifest valued, effective leadership styles, even somewhat more than men do, and are often associated with successful business organizations. Attitudinal prejudice against women leaders appears to have lessened substantially, although even now there are more Americans who prefer male than female bosses. People say that they would vote for a woman for president; however, only slightly more than half of Americans indicate that the country is ready to have a female president. Because of the remaining prejudicial barriers, women face challenges as leaders that men do not face, especially in settings where female leaders are nontraditional. Such signs of advantage mixed with disadvantage and trust mixed with distrust are contradictory only on the surface. They are manifestations of gender relations that have changed dramatically yet have not arrived at equality between the sexes.

Anick Tolbize (2008), Among the characteristics attributed to Xers life, the following appear most often. They aspire more than previous generations to achieve a balance between work and life they are more independent, autonomous and self-reliant than previous generations. They value continuous learning and skill development. They have strong technical skills, are results focused, and are “ruled by a sense of accomplishment and not the clock. Xers naturally question authority figures and are not intimidated by them. They can tolerate work as long as it is fun Although they are individualistic, they 2may also like teamwork, more so than boomers.

Peter C. Verhoef and Peter S.H. Leeflang (2009), The accountability and innovativeness of the marketing department represent the two major drivers of its influence. A marketing department's influence is related positively to market orientation, which in turn is related positively to firm performance. It also suggests a dual relationship between the marketing department's influence and market orientation. A key implication is that marketers should become more accountable and innovative to gain more influence.

Angelica L. Ditché and Hazel Joy A. Miranda (2017), Contractual employees' morale and human resource management are affected by the “end of contract” policy in the country. Emotions, attitude, satisfaction, and outlook that comprises employee morale; and hiring, training and development, and compensation and benefits operations of the human resource, effects are presumed.

According to Paul Legris, JohnInghamb and Pierre Collerette (2003), Information systems (IS) implementation is costly and has a relatively low success rate. Since the seventies, IS research has contributed to a better understanding of this process and its outcomes. The early efforts concentrated on the identification of factors that facilitated IS use. This produced a long list of items that proved to be of little practical value. It became obvious that, for practical reasons, the factors had to be grouped into a model in a way that would facilitate analysis of IS use. They conclude that TAM is a useful model but has to be integrated into a broader one which would include variables related to both human and social change processes, and to the acceptance of the innovation model.

Original Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

Statement of the Problem

This research assessed the acceptability of Admission Monitoring Management System (AMMS) for Informatics College, in Region VII during the academic year 2017 – 2018 as basis for a proposal.

Specifically, this answered the following questions:

1. What are the related information as regards respondents:
 - 1.1 age and gender,
 - 1.2 position,
 - 1.3 department, and
 - 1.4 employee status?
2. As assessed by the respondent group roles, what is the degree of functionality as to:
 - 2.1 Administrator,
 - 2.2 Technical/ & System Administrator
 - 2.3 Service Officer
 - 2.4 Manager,
 - 2.5 Center Manager
 - 2.6 Academics Head
 - 2.7 System Operators,
 - 2.8 Course Consultants
 - 2.9 Cashier
 - 2.10 Registrar
3. What is the acceptability of Admission Monitoring Management System (AMMS) as to Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) user motivations;
 - 3.1 perceived usefulness,
 - 3.2 perceived ease of use,
 - 3.3 attitude towards using, and
 - 3.4 behavioral intension to use?
4. What concordance agreement can be established among the aforementioned variables?
5. Based on the findings, what proposal can be crafted for Informatics College, Region VII?

Literature Review

This chapter primarily presents the different researches and other literatures from both foreign and local researchers, which have significant bearings on the variables included in the research. It focuses on several aspects that will help in the development of this study. The study is generally concentrating on the feasibility of creating an Admission Monitoring Management System of Informatics College, Region VII and to determine its acceptability to the different user roles as to Super Administrator: that enables the users to control the dataset system or he will be the one who manages the database management system, Administrator: this user will enable to manipulate the data entry of all the users of the system, User role: they are the one who control the flow of the admission process of the system, Manager role: the top level user who will use the reports in analyzing the over-all information that are coming from the Admission system so they will be able to use them for analysis. The literatures of this study come from books, "journals, articles, electronic materials such as PDF or E-Book, and other existing dissertations, foreign and local that are believed to be useful in the advancement of awareness concerning the study.

In conducting the study, some related literatures were useful in shedding additional direction to this investigation. User acceptance is defined as the demonstrable willingness within a user group to employ information technology for the tasks it is designed to support. Thus, the concept is not being applied to situations in which users claim they will employ it without providing evidence of use, or to the use of a technology for purposes unintended by the designers or procurers (e.g., using an Internet connection for personal entertainment in a work situation). Obviously, there is a degree of fuzziness here since actual usage is always likely to deviate slightly from idealized, planned usage, but the essence of acceptance theory is that such deviations are not significant; that is, the process of user acceptance of any information technology for intended purposes can be modeled and predicted. Lack of user acceptance is a significant impediment to the success of new information systems (GOULD ET AL; NICKERSON). In fact, users are often unwilling to use information systems which, if used, would result in impressive performance gains (e.g., ALAVI HENDERSON; SWANSON, 1988). Therefore, user acceptance has been viewed as the pivotal factor in determining the success or failure of any information system project (DAVIS, 1993).

Both practitioners and researchers have a strong interest in understanding why people accept information technology so that better methods for designing, evaluating, and predicting how users will respond to new technology can be developed. Although practically intertwined, design and evaluation are logically independent issues, as noted by DILLON, and it remains an open question in many instances how to translate usability evaluation results to specific interface design improvements. Acceptance theory seeks to extend the traditional model of user-centered design espoused in usability engineering approaches (e.g., NIELSEN) from questions of interface improvement towards predictions of likely usage.

Historically, developers and procurers of new technology may have been able to rely on authority to ensure that technology was used, at least in industrial/organizational contexts, though even the much-maligned scientific management of TAYLOR appealed to the motivational power of financial reward in encouraging workers to use the tools designed for them in the way in which they were told. However, current working practices, as well as the leisure and educational applications of information technology, render the search for predictive measures of acceptance more acute. As technological use spreads across society and organizations become more dependent on information technologies, the concern with designing information systems that will be used appropriately grows.

According to Jennifer Rowley (2005), information systems are a tool to support information management. Information systems are increasingly being used in organizations with the objective of providing competitive advantage. The information systems used by organizations can be grouped into different types such as transaction processing system, management information system, decision support system, executive information system, expert systems and office information system. Information

Technology has heralded the advent of the information society. The information society may be a “virtual society”. The concepts of the electronic classroom, the electronic office and electronic library have been explored. Information system poses a number of issues on society in general, including: changing employment patterns, archiving, and bibliographic control, security and data protection, intellectual property, marketplace issues and access. An registration system is basically included in one of the classifications of information system that is stated by the author, thus it serves as a tool to support information management with regards to the student data, enrollment fees information and other with a connection to the enrollment process. Every school gain competitive advantage of having this system for they will have the capacity on handling important information at ease and with security. The iterative implementation approach is a theory that eliminates problems of using a waterfall study. This is invented to avoid a linear and sequential development of study. The overall functionality of the system is broken down into feature sets. These features sets often based upon use cases from the analysis stage, containing group of individual features that are related, typically by a functional area (Stephen McHenry, 2010) Adopting the theory of Stephen McHenry which is known as the iterative implementation covers the breakdown of overall functionality of the system to a what he called feature set and those feature sets represents different process involve in an enrollment system. It helps locate what feature an enrollment system will have since that this kind of systems does many activities and processes.

As said by Dunn and Scott (2005), science and technology is the root of emerging innovations in this world. For many years now, a person in this field of expertise does not stop to reshape the landscape of today’s business world. Enrollment system has made huge impact into the school arena. It is a system that is built on innovative program strategies. It is a system that will help both the enrollment personnel-in-charge and the students to easily process the enrollment at a lesser time. Distinct from traditional enrollment, LAN enrollment system process large assortment of student records and provides efficient and consistent information services.

As stated by Holmes (2006), “The Internet is neither an extraordinary communication tool nor revolutionary. It simply represents the current stage in the development of human capabilities through written language, which itself derived from the spoken form.” That statement only shows that advancement in modern technology is at their highest peak. Nowadays, Web-based applications are widely used due to their ubiquity. Web-based enrollment system is currently emerging on markets for they are offering transaction convenience and service efficiency through the use of Internet. This system becomes a powerful tool in dealing with information management regarding enrollment transactions.

According to Forman (2007), continuing innovation in technologies can lead to organizational changes that range from improvement of day to day operation and for easy access it provides for the end users. Many schools today have adapted this innovation in offering of their services which is parallel with the concept of Tinn (2001), stated that the computerization responded to the call the office or any workplace to help their daily operation.

Malolos et.al (2002) stated that the study of automation is important in the sense time it minimizes the time and effort normally exerted in manual process. While Janes (2001) stated that computers are extremely reliable device and very powerful calculators with some great accessories applications like word processing problem for all of business activities, regardless of size, computers have three advantages over other type of office equipment that process information because computer are faster, more accurate more economical. Reyes (2005) task would be time consuming to accomplish manually and more practical with the aid of computers field in cabinet. According to Flores (2002), the automation is described simply as the substitution of machine control of human.

Dioso (2001) stated that computer assist careful intelligent planning, organizing, actuating and controlling. This maybe observed from the past that they monitor production activities, solve scientific

problem and help arrive in tentative answer to a multitude of involved conditions. Ralph M. Stair (1999) emphasized that the development of technology through the years have enabled us to do more with less effort. From the orientation of the light bulb to the industrial revolution and beyond, we have continuously tried to in a more efficient means of doing tasks.

Lewis (2002) stated that the reason for using computers vary from person to person. Some of the computers in business are to perform accuracy, to be as productivity, to decrease bottle necks or hassles to alter cash flows or to simplify elevate your status. Gold Chager et al (2003) said that computer as a device for processing information knew computer plays a significant role in their lives, but few are aware of just how pervasive role is.

Mane (2000) mentioned that the creation of the computer made the easier to accomplish task than by doing it manually, to have the direct access on straightforward answer just monitoring record where in the needs of computer make possible for everyone to get data in a particular need. We can consider that the computer is necessary and it is a productive tool for individual.

Forman (2007), continuing innovation in technologies can lead to organizational changes that range from improvement of day to day operation and for easy access it provides for the end users. Many schools today have adapted this innovation in offering of their services which is parallel with the concept of Tinn (2001), stated that the computerization responded to the call the office or any workplace to help their daily operation. Computer- Based Enrollment system Halili, M.C.N. (2004) that man's actions are just involuntary movements especially when time allow to plan his next action. These responses pass through the process of reasoning and analysis. Hutchinson et.al (2001) stated that file is a collection of related records. Examples are the entire student's courses card for Anthropology 101 or the transcript of all courses in the register's office.

Bryan (2006) emphasized the information system is a set of people, procedures and resources that collects, transforms and disseminates information in an organization to do's ends rely on many types of information system (IS). They might include simple manual information system and informal system and also computer-based information system that uses hardware, software telecommunication and other forms of information technology (IT). Sander (2002) computers are an intelligence amplifier that can free human to use their time effectively. Because a computer is a fast and accurate electronic symbol or data manipulating system that design automatically accept and store input data process and procedure output results under the direction of the stored program or instruction. Tows and (2005), stated that database is instructed collection of data. The data may be about people, product events in short, any type of information is to manage the collection of data for reporting and making decision.

Adamski (2007), give some advantages of database processing first economy of scale getting more information from some amount of data, sharing data balancing conflicting requirement, enforcement of standard, controlled redundancy consisting integrity security, flexibility and responsiveness, increase programmers' productivity, improve program maintenance and data independence. Perkins (1999) stated that computer has an impressive impact upon business, governmental organization; bank and all sorts of organization and on how they are operating and manage. Alcaria (2004) explained that the use of computer is continue to grow, the need for a timelier information and data processing comes on demand keeping the records of any manual operations need the application of computer because handling it manually will only be conflicting.

Alice H. Eagly (2007), Research has established a mixed picture for contemporary female leadership. Women leaders on average manifest valued, effective leadership styles, even somewhat more than men do, and are often associated with successful business organizations. Attitudinal prejudice against women leaders appears to have lessened substantially, although even now there are more Americans who prefer male than female bosses. People say that they would vote for a woman for president; however, only

slightly more than half of Americans indicate that the country is ready to have a female president. Because of the remaining prejudicial barriers, women face challenges as leaders that men do not face, especially in settings where female leaders are nontraditional. Such signs of advantage mixed with disadvantage and trust mixed with distrust are contradictory only on the surface. They are manifestations of gender relations that have changed dramatically yet have not arrived at equality between the sexes.

Anick Tolbize (2008), Among the characteristics attributed to Xers life, the following appear most often. They aspire more than previous generations to achieve a balance between work and life they are more independent, autonomous and self-reliant than previous generations. They value continuous learning and skill development. They have strong technical skills, are results focused, and are “ruled by a sense of accomplishment and not the clock. Xers naturally question authority figures and are not intimidated by them. They can tolerate work as long as it is fun Although they are individualistic, they 2may also like teamwork, more so than boomers.

Peter C. Verhoef and Peter S.H. Leeflang (2009), The accountability and innovativeness of the marketing department represent the two major drivers of its influence. A marketing department's influence is related positively to market orientation, which in turn is related positively to firm performance. It also suggests a dual relationship between the marketing department's influence and market orientation. A key implication is that marketers should become more accountable and innovative to gain more influence.

Angelica L. Diche and Hazel Joy A. Miranda (2017), Contractual employees' morale and human resource management are affected by the “end of contract” policy in the country. Emotions, attitude, satisfaction, and outlook that comprises employee morale; and hiring, training and development, and compensation and benefits operations of the human resource, effects are presumed.

According to Paul Legris, JohnInghamb and Pierre Collette (2003), Information systems (IS) implementation is costly and has a relatively low success rate. Since the seventies, IS research has contributed to a better understanding of this process and its outcomes. The early efforts concentrated on the identification of factors that facilitated IS use. This produced a long list of items that proved to be of little practical value. It became obvious that, for practical reasons, the factors had to be grouped into a model in a way that would facilitate analysis of IS use. They conclude that TAM is a useful model, but has to be integrated into a broader one which would include variables related to both human and social change processes, and to the acceptance of the innovation model.

Based on the researcher by Rodriguez Jaime, Luis Francisco's Student Acceptance of Online Enrollment Processes in a Higher Education Institution of Walden University (2014). The study demonstrated the reliability of the modified TAM tool as a viable model that enables enrollment managers and academic administrators the analysis of the acceptance of their enrollment processes from the perspective of their students. The analysis of the opinion of the student as customers regarding the perception of the online enrollment demonstrated that the students as users perceived that the online enrollment processes rendered by the institution are useful, ease to useand satisfy their needs as users. Due the low response of the participants the results of this study did not demonstrate the correlation between the student perception of the online enrollment processes and the acceptance of the processes. This study was unable to demonstrate the assumption that the acceptance of the online enrollment increases as the student perception increases improving their usage and satisfaction due the lack of response of the participants.

According to Chet Claar, Laura Portolese Dias and Robert Shields (2014), The regression analysis provided insight into relationships between variables from the TAM model perspective. It appears most of the TAM model variables are relationship dependent, for example, perceived ease of use does impact perceive usefulness. Likewise, perceived usefulness and ease of use does impact attitude toward using. The perceive usefulness does impact behavioral intentions as well. While most of the hypotheses related to the TAM model are supported by this study, the surprising exception is H6. One would expect behavioral

intention to use would positively impact actual use. The regression analysis found this is not the case. Possible reasons for this could include student disappointment with actual use, or lack of actual use. In addition, because students do not actually have a choice to use the LMS system, behavioral intention relationships could have been skewed. Regression analysis showed few demographic variable relationships. Of the analysis, the only relationships found were: age and perceived usefulness; education and perceived usefulness; and education and ease of use. Reasons for this might include the greater the age, the greater the understanding and importance of usefulness, or concern with usefulness. It is possible younger generations have less concern about usefulness, given the vast experience with technology. It is possible the less education, the more concern a student may have for ease of use. While the more educated, there is an assumption and confidence from the student to navigate a new system. Gender and race did not impact any of the TAM variables, therefore H8 and H9 are accepted, as the investigators did not expect either of these variables would influence acceptance of a LMS. The implications and significance of this study can be important to both LMS providers as well as universities. When universities are marketing and surveying students for use of a new learning management system, they should focus their efforts on ease of use and usefulness of the new system, as opposed to focus marketing efforts in less importance areas. Attitude toward using, actual use, and behavioral intention to use should be secondary marketing efforts. In addition, LMS's should focus their orientation materials on ease of use and usefulness for maximum acceptance of their technology. While in a study conducted by Cayabyab (2007), many problems and difficulties were identified in the existing system of Dagupan City National High School (DCNHS). These major concerns are affecting the efficient enrollment system of students. Security of the students' records were found to be at high risk. The current system may fail to protect some important documents. It has also untimely and inefficient report generation. A computerized system for DCNHS shall result to a significant increase in the number of enrollees Network-Based Enrollment system Conde (2007) in his study entitled "Network-based Enrollment System of Paete National High School cited that the manual process of enrollment and manual handling of information and reports of the students is very laborious one.

Garcia (2002) created the "LSPC Enrollment System", the study can be a great help to persons concerned during the enrollment period, the registrar, instructor of the students as they retrieval necessary information when needed and lessen the burden manually browsing over enrollment slip for record purposes Saayo et.al (2008) developed the system "Network based automated Enrollment and grading system for Morong National High School. Due to increasing population of the institution, and the school currently implementing the manual system, every student spends a lot of time during enrollment period, such as paying their tuition fees and processing the school requirements.

Valina et.al (2009), in this work entitled "Network-based student Permanent Record keeping and Enrollment System of Balian National High School". This System was made to lessen the time and effort exerted by both student and school employees. It is also made to give accurate reports and keep records of every students every students and for easy and fast way of enrollment. Soria (2006), constructed a system entitled "Network-based Computerized inventory System for the supply office of the LSPC main campus. With the advancement of technology, devices and machines were improve , developed and inverted to cope up with the need of new world. There are different systems designed for reliable, efficient and very useful to the user.

Cabang et al. (2003) developed the 'computerized Students Record Monitoring System of Siniloan National High School', Computerized Student data will be exceedingly helped to the user through continuous management of the School. It could help the registrar for a less effort services in the institutions especially in updating, printing and deleting student's record. Velasco (2002) Study entitled "Maulawin National High School Student Information System" cited that maintaining students, records manually is a

very difficult task and time consuming. In that case, computerization system that can help and handle 17 this data needed to speed up the process of student's record keeping and to promote and reliability.

Cura et al. (2004), Designed system entitled "computerized inventory system of office of the supply in LSPU" is capable of handling voluminous data about the flow of item insurance and reply to the flow of items' issuance and return in supply office Torres et al. (2002), conducted a study that resolves around the importance computerization of student information. This study was conducted with the hope that it would help minimize time and effort in processing student's information in Maulawin National High School. The basic feature of this study is after the storage and access of retrieving and updating the data.

METHODS

Research Design

This study will utilize the descriptive-survey method of research. The questionnaire was used as an instrument of data. The descriptive developmental research design was the method used to determine the level of acceptability of the Admission Monitoring Management System as to its design and functionality. The evaluators were composed of the Administrator, Academics Head, Course Consultants, Cashier, Registrar, Service officer and Technical personnel; a higher education institution located in the hearth of Region VII, Cebu. In this study, a computerized Admission Monitoring System in the said educational institution was developed using an Object-Oriented Programming Language (PHP) and evaluated thru TAM (Technology Acceptance Model).

Flow of the Study

Developing a system used different tools and techniques to solve the problems encountered by the research. The research used step by step procedure to overcome and solve the problems. Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is a model by Davis (1989) which was developed after improving his ideas previously-used in his doctoral dissertation that states the acceptance of the new technology of end-users can be formed by the aid of (1) Perceived usefulness, (2) Perceived ease of use, (3) Attitude Towards using and (4) Behavioral Intension to Use. Technology Acceptance Model guided the ideas which defending that success of the information systems – technologically – can be achieved not only by technical and administrative features of the users but also by their personal characteristics, expectations and perceptions; user's perception on various issues can affect this success as well.

Figure 2. *The Flow of the Study*

This study examines the user factor in order to determine the success of Admission Monitoring Management System software which was built in a customized application system using HTML, CSS, JavaScript, NodeJS Framework and NunJukes engine and GIT BASH command line shell, within the framework of TAM. Some firms use customized software’s prove that perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness have a positive and statistically significant effect on the implementation success as well as on perceived organizational performance. These results reveal that all hypotheses have been supported and the study is coherent the findings of similar studies wit. The researcher used step by step procedure to overcome and solve the problems. Step one is to communicate with the Center Manager for the approval and interviews for the following respondents: Administrator, Academics Head, Cahier, Registrar, Course Consultants, Service Officer, Technical Personnel and Administrator to gather necessary information in solving the institution’s problems. Having gathered the necessary information and the gathering of data was accurately analyzed, identified the scopes and limitations. The researchers then follow the Systems Development Life Cycle procedure to build the Admission Monitoring Management System which needs the following phases; Planning, Systems Analysis and Requirements, Systems Design, Development, Integration and Testing and Implementation Operations and Maintenance

The Input Phase, it includes what related information in the Admission Monitoring Management System regarding respondents. Admission Monitoring Management System developed as to the following features and the Acceptability of Admission Monitoring Management System as to Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) user motivations.

The Process Phase, it includes Evaluation and Interpretation of the data presented and Conclusion and Recommendation. The research and it also included the survey questionnaire, and the statistical data that were computed using the weighted mean, and percentage.

The Output Phase, shows the Sustainability Plan and recommendations and the Behavioral Intention and the acceptability the Technology Acceptance Program introduce by the researcher by using

Admission Monitoring Management System and having passed the system testing, Admission Monitoring Management System is now accepted by Informatics College Region VII.

Research Environment

Information and Communication Technology and Admission management is an important issue, since it is well recognized that senior managers in schools have a major impact upon school management practices, and that the use of Information and Communication Technology within schools is permeating aspects to the extent that it will impact upon the practice of all staff (both teaching and non-teaching personnel). Informatics Philippines is a member of the Informatics global group with its main headquarters in Singapore. Our organization is engaged in training and education in fields of Information Technology and business, offering degree and diploma programs. Informatics are also affiliated with Universities from the UK, Australia, and US. The National Computing Center from Manchester, UK (NCC, UK) and Informatics Academy from Singapore validate our Higher Education programs. Informatics College, Region VII – Cebu, Consolacion and Cagayan the researcher location of the study is an International Information Technology school that is capable of adopting and implementing an Automated System since; the entire school premises is spread over 2 floors with lecture rooms and are equipped with modern teaching aids. With 3 computers laboratory consists of over 72 high-end PC's networked, including an Electronic Learning Library. Each Personnel on their own department has his own computer and that includes 1 computer for the faculty department which is very useful in making their reports. And 5 Laptops and 5 LCD projectors are issued when teachers are having their lectures and a server room for its networking capability. The research environment human resources with an individual who have the knowledge and skills to use a computer and other related technology. All Human Resources are computer literate which involves learning on how to access information and perform basic operations on a computer. However, because computers are much more advanced now a days in terms of access, operation and overall use, computer literacy includes many more types of cognitive and technical skills, from understanding text and visual symbols, to turning devices on and off or accessing parts of an operating system through menus. The Technical Departments of Informatics College can provide assistance to the user's technology product such as Admission Monitoring Management System and other computer related problems. With a fiber optics internet connectivity of up to 300mbps. And that includes all the software are License product.

Informatics also offers short IT training courses for corporations and individuals to get high-end skills in information technology, providing professionals with a competitive edge to succeed in the IT industry. Equipped with state-of-art equipment and flexible platforms, Informatics' committed team of trainers continues to train and upgrade themselves in response to the rapid developments in ICT. Informatics is well- poised to provide advanced training for professionals and place them in the forefront of information technology.

Figure 3. *The Location of the Study – Informatics Region VII*

Because of their growing clientele base, increasing scope and increasing traffic on the road, the company is experiencing considerable delays in releasing its reports on time. Another factor contributing to the delay is that data are encoded manually and filed in different personal computers making traceability also a problem factor. Even though Informatics Philippines is one of the leading ICT Schools in the Philippines, Informatics is still looking for a good Admission Monitoring Management System. And now Informatics College, Region VII uses an Admission Monitoring Management System that will provide collaboration between some Departments and streamline the process of deriving, approving and delivering test results to its department. An Admission Monitoring Management System will allow the company to effectively collaborate in processing test data and approving the same even if they are not of the same area from the office. At the same time an Admission Monitoring Management System will automatically deliver the day-to-day report without delay. Proposing to develop an Admission Monitoring Management System (AMMS) that will provide collaboration between Informatics Departments and streamline the process of deriving, approving and delivering test results to its respondents. The proposed system will allow Department who is involved in the admission process in the company to effectively collaborate.

Research Respondents

The respondent groups of the study are the intended users of the Admission Monitoring Management System categories according to roles as Administrators, Managers and System Operators. The Administrators are composed of Service Officers and Technical Personnel, while the Managers are Center Managers and Academic Heads and the System Operators are composed of Course Consultants, Cashiers and Registrars of Informatics College, Region VII during the school year 2017 –

2018. They are the respondents of the study since they are the users of the Admission Monitoring Management System.

Based on the actual data gathered, there was a total population of 31 respondents. There is no sampling taken because the respondent of the study is the entire population. The distribution of the respondents is represented in Table 1.

Table 1

Schools	Population Roles	Population
Cebu	Administrator	2
	Manager	2
	System Operators	7
Consolacion	Administrator	2
	Manager	2
	System Operators	6
Cagayan De Oro	Administrator	2
	Manager	2
	System Operators	6
Total		31

Data Gathering Instrument

The instrument used in gathering and the collection data were the structured questionnaire, interviews, and research. Given that the study focused on technology acceptance program, the questionnaire was so constructed as guided by the theory of technology acceptance model. The structured questionnaire was composed of three parts: The First part was to assess the users Perceived Usefulness and Ease of Use when using the Admission Monitoring Management System where the respondent rated very statement. The Second part assessed the Attitudes towards using the Admission Monitoring Management System in terms of computer system usability. The Last part was done by determining the behavioral intention of the user to use the system and its acceptability to use the system for change. The study conducted interviews using the structured questionnaire to understand the respondents' observation on the current computer trends that they know. This was used in gathering data which is necessary to make the Admission Monitoring Management System more acceptable to the users. The data and information gathered were analyzed to understand fully the routine of the Admission Monitoring Management System and how it is useful to the institution and to know other possible solutions that will help in making the proposed Admission Monitoring Management System.

Research Procedures

For the purpose of determining the functionality of the questionnaire as an instrument of data collection, the researcher will be conducting a dry run on 30 respondents of informatics College employees. They will be instructed to answer all questions and to give their suggestions for improving the questionnaire. The accomplished questionnaire was collected responses will be tallied. The researcher then made an item analysis of the questions. Most commented that the questions or items be qualified with adjectives. Considering these comments, the researcher recast the questionnaire affixing the adjectives based on the ideal set-up or organizational goals. Another dry run will be conducted on same number of respondents and a reasonable range of variation on their responses was noted. Hence, the questionnaire will be reproduced, distributed, collected, and tallied.

Gathering of Data

Permission to conduct this study was obtained from the Center Manager of Informatics College office. Upon the granting of permission and the approval of this study concept and the proposal design, the researcher let the respondents used the Admission Monitoring Management System and distributed copies of the questionnaire among the employees according to its Role. During the administration of the questionnaire to the respondents, the researcher made himself available in order to answer the respondents' questions thru researcher's personal contact number.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The following statistical tools will be used to remedy the data gathered in this study.

Simple Percentage

This was utilized to get the profile of the respondents;

- i. Age
- ii. Gender
- iii. Position
- iv. Department
- v. Employee Status

Weighted Mean

This was utilized to determine the adequacy of material resources and the perceptions of the respondent's users Role as to the extent in the acceptability of Technology Acceptance Program in Informatics College, Region VII along its Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Attitude Towards Using and Behavioral Intension to Use.

Concordance

The degree of agreement among the aforementioned variables.

Scoring Procedure

The accomplished questionnaire was collected and the responses tabulated. The sum of the values of each item distribution was used to determine the mean. The mean is for the examination and analysis of a large collection taken from the evaluation of the Admission Monitoring Management System. It is helpful to be able to present a number that provides the summary for the Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and Attitude Towards using and the Behavioral Intention to Use the proposed and the users respond to the Admission Monitoring Management System.

Descriptive rating for the computed mean is as follows:

Scale	Interpretation	Parameters
4.20 – 5.00	Well Developed	The respondents believed that the Admission Monitoring Management System module solved the problem. The level of judgement was Strongly Agree or 100% favorable.
3.40 – 4.19	Partially Developed	The respondents believed that the Admission Monitoring Management System module solved the problem. The level of judgement was Agree or 80% favorable.
2.60 – 3.39	Developed	The respondents believed that the Admission Monitoring Management System module solved the problem. The level of judgement was Neither Agree or Disagree or 50% favorable.
1.80 – 2.59	Poorly Developed	The respondents believed that the Admission Monitoring Management System module solved the problem. The level of judgement was Disagree or 40% favorable.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Developed	The respondents believed that the Admission Monitoring Management System module solved the problem. The level of judgement was Strongly Disagree or 20% favorable.

To answer question on the assessment of the degree to which how the Admission Monitoring Management System was develop for each Role of deliverables in the company, range values was assigned to Descriptive rating indicated by each item.

Descriptive rating for the computed mean is as follows:

Scale	Interpretation	Parameters
4.20 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	The respondents believed that Admission Monitoring Management System would enhance his or her job performance, free of effort, Attitude and intension to use. The level of judgement was Strongly Agree or 100% favorable.
3.40 – 4.19	Agree	The respondents believed that Admission Monitoring Management System would enhance his or her job performance free of effort, Attitude and intension to use. The level of judgement was Agree or 80% favorable.
2.60 – 3.39		The respondents believed that Admission Monitoring Management System would enhance his or her job performance free of effort, Attitude and intension to use. The level of judgement was Neither Agree or Disagree or 50% favorable.

	Neither Agree or Disagree	
1.80 – 2.59	Disagree	The respondents believed that Admission Monitoring Management System would enhance his or her job performance free of effort, Attitude and intension to use. The level of judgement was Disagree or 40% favorable.
1.00 – 1.79	Strongly Disagree	The respondents believed that Admission Monitoring Management System would enhance his or her job performance free of effort, Attitude and intension to use. The level of judgement was Strongly Disagree or 20% favorable.

To answer question on the assessment of the degree to which a person believes that using the proposed Admission Monitoring Management System would enhance his or her job performance, free of effort, Attitude and intension to use, range values was assigned to Descriptive rating indicated by each item.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The data obtain from the respondent groups were presented and analyzed in this chapter. This contains data regarding related information as regards to respondent’s age and gender, position, departments and employee status. It contains data that could assess the respondent’s group role to the degree of functionality as to Administrators, Managers and System Operators. Obtains related information to the acceptability of Admission Monitoring Management System (AMMS) in accordance to Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) user’s motivation as to perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, attitude towards using, and behavioral intension to use. And to answer the concordance correlation that established among aforementioned variables.

Related Information of the Respondents

This section discusses the following respondents profile of Informatics College, Region VII with the following respondents; Center Managers, Academics Heads, Service Officers, Technical Personnel, Registrars, Cashiers and Course Consultants.

Age and Gender

Presented in this portion was the respondent’s age and gender profile. Age and Gender of the respondents is one of the most important characteristics in understanding their views about the particular problems; by and large age and gender indicates level of maturity of individuals in that sense age and gender becomes important to examine the response. Table 2 shows the respondents age range from 50 – 60yrs, 30 – 40yrs and 20yrs above. It shows the Male and Female gender according to the respondents’ groups by Administrator, Mangers and System Operators. Data on age and gender are presented on Table 2.

Table 2. *Age and Gender of the Respondents*

Age and Gender	Administrators						Managers						System Operators						Total Mean		
	Male			Female			Male			Female			Male			Female					
	Ce	Co	Ca	Ce	Co	Ca	Ce	Co	Ca	Ce	Co	Ca	Ce	Co	Ca	Ce	Co	Ca			
50 - 60						1												1			2
30 - 40	1	1	1				1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2		2	2				17
20 - 29	1	1											2	1				2	5		12
Total per Position	2	2	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	4	3	0	3	4	5			31
Total per Gender	5			1			3			3			7			12					
Total per Area	6						6						19								
Total Male																			15		
Total Female																			16		

Legend: Ce means Cebu, Co means Consolacion, Ca means Cagayan De Oro

Table 2 describes the age and the gender of the respondents. As a whole, there are more females than males in the sample. Specifically, around 51.61 percent (that is, 16 out of the 31 respondents) of them are females, while the males are only around 48.3 percent of them (that is, 15 out of 31 respondents). Interestingly, the males are dominating in the administration department while females are dominating in the system operation department. Male is dominant on the Administrator since the Hardware and Software problems of the school is more on the Information Technology and the assigned personnel should be a computer literate people in an advance level understanding. Based on the gender representation majority of personnel are dominated by Female when it comes to the work force since mostly are assigned on themarketing personnel and the school president prefers female as the top managers of the school. Research has established a mixed picture for contemporary female leadership. Women leaders on average manifest valued, effective leadership styles, even somewhat more than men do, and are often associated with successful business organizations (Alice H. Eagly ,2007: Female Leadership Advantage and Disadvantage: Resolving the Contradictions).

The age of the respondents ranges from 20 to 60 years old, and most of them are in the middle age group that is, within the age bracket of 30 to 40 years old. Most of them are on the middle group age since the Manager of each Center prefers this age bracket. Surprisingly, there are only two (2) of them who are in the old age group (that is, within the age bracket 50 to 60 years old). Two of the employees are in the old age group because these two are the Heads of their own department. But the majority respondents at the age bracket of 30 yrs. old to 40yrs. old especially who has a responsibility in the institution. This implies that among the characteristics attributed to Xers life, the following appear most often. They aspire more than previous generations to achieve a balance between work and life they are more independent, autonomous and self-reliant than previous generations. They value continuous learning and skill development. They have strong technical skills, are results focused, and are “ruled by a sense of accomplishment and not the clock. Xers naturally question authority figures and are not intimidated by them. They can tolerate work as long as it is fun Although they are individualistic, they may also like teamwork, more so than boomers (Anick Tolbize, 2008: Generational differences in the workplace, rtc3.umn.edu).

Position

Position is usually defined as any employment, though usually above manual labor. The positions of the respondents assigned to the three areas namely: Cebu, Consolacion and Cagayan De Oro; Course Consultants from Cebu has the highest number of employees as shown in Table 3.

Table 3. *Position of the Respondents*

POSITION	AREA			FREQUENCY	PERCENT (%)
	Cebu	Consolacion	Cagayan De Oro		
Center Manager	1	1	1	3	9.68
Academics Head	1	1	1	3	9.68
Service Officer	1	1	1	3	9.68
Cashier	1	1	1	3	9.68
Registrar	1	1	1	3	9.68
Course Consultants	5	4	4	13	41.94
Technical Personnel	1	1	1	3	9.68
Total	11	10	10	31	100.00

In Table 3, the positions of the respondents are as follows: center manager, academics head, service officer, cashier, registrar, course consultants and technical personnel. Center Manager must see the total enrollee so that she can handle the security, operational and financial matters while overseeing the admission process, the Academics Head position is very crucial since they are the one who will make the school calendar and plot the subjects schedule of the entire semester as well as they are the one who can evaluate the student subjects enrolled, the Service Officer and the Technical Personnel used to handle the entire hardware and software facilities of the college, the cashier responsibility is to make sure that the students pay the tuition fee and make reports on who's students still have balances from the previous semester, the Registrar duty is very crucial also in the college since they keep all the information of the students from personal to their academics records and the course consultants responsibility is to make sure that there are enrollees in Senior High and College. It shows that most of the respondents, roughly 41.9 percent of them, are course consultants. It implies that the driving force of academe is concentrated in the course consultant positions. The course consultants as the driving force the college since they are the life and blood of the college by bringing more students to enroll in the said college. The other positions are only taking a small part of the college considering that these positions are either administrative or support service in nature. It is also important to note that the positions are also evenly spread among the three areas. The position of the respondents was equally distributed by the three areas as to Cebu, Consolacion and Cagayan De Oro and it implies that the Information Technology organization of the institution is ideal and will distributed and therefore the organization is systematic and organized.

Department

There are currently four departments in the college – the Administration, Marketing, Staff and Technical. Each department is expected to perform certain function. The Administration is composed of Managers and Academics Head they are the top management of the school. The Marketing department is

composed of Course Consultant and the Marketing Head who are the promoting the services of the college. The Staff department is expected to intermingling with the Course Consultant and Academics during the admission process and they are the Registrar and the Cashier. And the Technical department is composed of the Service Officer and the Technical Personnel who will manage the maintenance of the school facilities. The distribution of the respondents among the four departments among the three areas is shown in Table 4.

Table 4. *Distribution of Respondents among the Departments*

DEPARTMENT	AREA			FREQUENCY	PERCENT (%)
	Cebu	Consolacion	Cagayan De Oro		
Administration	2	2	2	6	19.35
Marketing	5	4	4	13	41.94
Staff	3	3	3	9	29.03
Technical	1	1	1	3	9.68
Total	11	10	10	31	100.00

In the table, approximately 41.94 percent of the respondents are working in the Marketing department, around 29.03 percent of them are in Staff department, roughly 19.35 percent of them are working as administrators, and only about 9.68 percent of them are in Technical department. Most of the respondents are working in the Marketing Department since they have the most personnel in the area and as mandated by the president of the institution that they are the most vital part of the department because it measure the institution’s entrepreneurial orientation. The accountability and innovativeness of the marketing department represent the two major drivers of its influence. A marketing department's influence is related positively to market orientation, which in turn is related positively to firm performance. It also suggests a dual relationship between the marketing department's influence and market orientation. A key implication is that marketers should become more accountable and innovative to gain more influence (Peter C. Verhoef, Peter S.H. Leeflang ,2009).

Employee Status

The respondents are either employed as permanent, contractual, casual or probationary. The table below shows the employment status of the respondents in the three areas as shown in table 5.

Table 5. *Employment Status of the Respondents*

EMPLOYMENT STATUS	AREA			FREQUENCY	PERCENT (%)
	Cebu	Consolacion	Cagayan De Oro		
Permanent	11	10	7	28	90.32
Contractual				0	0.00
Casual				0	0.00
Probationary			3	3	9.68
Total	11	10	10	31	100.00

In Table 5, most of the respondents have permanent status of employment in the college, that is, around 90.32 percent of them. The rest are still in probationary period of employment. Most respondents are permanent since some of them are rendering more than 2 yrs. These respondents in probationary status are just being hired by the college. In the area of Cagayan De Oro 9.68 percent or only 3 employees in the probationary status because they are the replacement of those personnel resigned from there service in these area. It implies that the institution values its employees and builds better relationship. The data also shows that the company did not practice the ENDO End of Contract policy which is more common in the Philippines industry. Contractual employees' morale and human resource management are affected by the "end of contract" policy in the country. Emotions, attitude, satisfaction, and outlook that comprises employee morale; and hiring, training and development, and compensation and benefits operations of the human resource, effects are presumed (Angelica L. Ditché and Hazel Joy A. Miranda, 2017).

Functionality of Admission Monitoring Management System

This portion presents the data to which describes the functionality of the Admission Monitoring Manage System. And the ability of Admission Monitoring Management System to do the work for which it was intended on each module and to perform to verify that Admission Monitoring Management System performs and functions correctly according to design specifications. During functionality testing we check the core application functions, text input, menu functions and installation and respondents' manipulation on the Admission Monitoring Manage System.

Administrator

Composed of the Technical Personnel and the Service Officer they are the one who will control the Admission Monitoring Management System for the upkeep, configuration, and reliable operation of computer systems; especially multi-user computers, such as servers. Administrator responsibility are usually charged with installing, supporting, and maintaining servers or other computer systems, and planning for and responding to service outages and other problems according to area; Cebu, Consolacion and Cagayan De Oro.

Technical Personnel. This section presents the degree of functionality of the Admission Monitoring Management System as perceived by the Technical/Systems Administrators as shown in Table 6. The Admission Monitoring Management System is divided in to several components such as User Management, Maintenance management, Password management and User Log Management.

Service Officer. This section discusses the degree of functionality of the Admission Monitoring Management System, as perceived by the Service Office. The components of Admission Monitoring Management System that involve the service officers are the assigning student ID numbers, processing ID, user management, and password management as shown in Table 6.

Table 6. *Degree of Functionality of the Admission Monitoring Management System as perceived by the Administrator Module*

FUNCTIONALITY OF ADMISSION MONITORING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM	Cebu		Consolacion		Cagayan de Oro		Mean	Vd
	X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd		
Technical Personnel								
1. User management	5.0	WD	4.0	D	5.0	WD	4.7	WD
Creating user View	5	WD	4	D	5	WD	4.7	WD
Assigning user role	5	WD	4	D	5	WD	4.7	WD
Updating/deleting user	5	WD	4	D	5	WD	4.7	WD

User logging	5	WD	4	D	5	WD	4.7	WD
2. Maintenance management	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	4.8	WD	4.9	WD
Disaster recovery	5	WD	5	WD	4.5	WD	4.8	WD
Generating backup	5	WD	5	WD	4	D	4.7	WD
Repairing Database	5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5.0	WD
Password recovering	5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5.0	WD
3. Password management	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	4.8	WD	4.9	WD
View Password	5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5.0	WD
Assigning user password	5	WD	5	WD	4	D	4.7	WD
Updating/deleting user password	5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5.0	WD
Assign Auto password	5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5.0	WD
4. User Log Management	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
View user Total Log	5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5.0	WD
View user Log Dates	5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5.0	WD
5. Assigning student ID#.	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
6. Processing ID	4.0	D	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	4.7	WD
7. Course Consulting Management	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
8. Registering Management	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
9. Servicing Management	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
10. Administrating Management	4.0	D	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	4.7	WD
Total Mean of Technical personnel	4.8	WD	4.9	WD	5.0	WD	4.9	WD
SUB MEAN	4.9							WD
Service Officers								
1. Assigning student ID#	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
2. Processing ID	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
3. User Management	4.8	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	4.9	WD
Creating View user	5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5.0	WD
Assigning user role	5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5.0	WD
Updating/deleting user	5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5.0	WD
User logging	4	D	5	WD	5	PaD	4.7	WD
4. Password management	4.0	D	5.0	WD	4.8	WD	4.9	WD
Viewing Password	4	D	5	WD	5	WD	4.7	WD
Assigning user password	4	D	5	WD	5	WD	4.7	WD
Updating/deleting user password	4	D	5	WD	5	WD	4.7	WD
Assign Auto password	4	D	5	WD	5	WD	4.7	WD
Total Mean of Service Officer	4.7	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	4.9	WD
SUB MEAN	4.9							WD
Total Mean	4.9							WD

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Well Developed (WD), 3.40 – 4.19 Developed (D), 2.60 – 3.39 Partially Developed (PaD), 1.80 – 2.59 Poorly Developed (PoD), 1.00 – 1.79 Not Developed (ND)

Table 6 reveals that the college as a whole has a well-developed Admission Monitoring Management System as perceived by the Technical/Systems Administrators from the three areas. This means that the systems in user management, maintenance management, password management, user log management, assigning student ID numbers, processing ID, course consulting management, registering management, servicing management, and administrating management are described as well developed. Although the three areas are generally perceived to have a well-developed system, but Cagayan de Oro area has the highest mean score of 5.0, which is described as well-developed and Cebu area has the lowest mean

score of 4.8, which is also described as well developed. Cebu area has the lowest mean perhaps they want the old process of admitting the students or the way how they treated the admission process. Cagayan De Oro generally has the highest mean score because ever since they do not have an automated not even a semi-automated system in process in admitting the students.

By looking into the components of the Admission Monitoring Management System in each of the areas, Cebu has well developed systems in user management, maintenance management, password management, user log management, assigning student ID numbers, course consulting management, registering management, and servicing management; while developed in processing ID and administrating management. In Consolacion area, they also responded to have a well-developed systems in maintenance management, password management, user log management, assigning student ID numbers, processing ID, course consulting management, registering management, servicing management, and administrating management; while in user management, it is described as developed. And in Cagayan de Oro area, all the components in Admission Monitoring Management System have well developed systems. All areas in the Technical/System Administrators agrees and accepted that the Admission Monitoring Management System functionality are well developed. All area has the highest acceptability and responded a well-developed Admission Monitoring Management System functionality because they are more oriented of the system by the researcher.

In Table 6, the college as a whole has a well-developed Admission Monitoring Management System as perceived by the Service offices from the three areas. This means that the systems in assigning student ID numbers, processing ID, user management, and password management are described as well developed. Although the three areas are generally perceived to have a well-developed system, the Consolacion and Cagayan de Oro areas have roughly the same mean scores while Cebu has the lowest mean score of 4.7, which is described as well developed. By looking into the components of the Admission Monitoring Management System in each of the areas, the Consolacion and Cagayan de Oro have well developed systems in all the four components; while Cebu has well developed systems in assigning student ID numbers, processing ID, and user management, and developed in password management. All areas in the Service Officers agrees and accepted that the Admission Monitoring Management System functionality are well developed. All area has the highest acceptability and responded a well-developed Admission Monitoring Management System functionality because they are more oriented of the system by the researcher.

Managers

Composed of the Center Manager and the Academics Head they are the one who will interpret and appraise information coming from the Admission Monitoring Management System; the top person that has the authority to make decisions in accordance to the company policies and guidelines and analyze reports generated by Admission Monitoring Management System according to area; Cebu, Consolacion and Cagayan De Oro.

Center Manager. This section explains the degree of functionality of the Admission Monitoring Management System as perceived by the Center Managers in the three areas. Viewing Registration Form for payment, Viewing/Student's Record, Viewing Previous/old matriculation payment needed for current enrollment, Viewing/Printing Schedule, Viewing Teachers Loading, Viewing Subjects Schedule, Viewing Registration Form for payment, Viewing Student's Record, Viewing of Enrollment Summary, Viewing of Master List, Viewing SHS Strand Categorization and Viewing College Course Categorization are the components in the Admission Monitoring Management System that involve the center managers.

Academics Head. This section shows the degree of functionality of the Admission Monitoring Management System as perceived by the Academics Head. Academic heads have to look into the following

components: plotting of subject’s schedule, viewing/printing schedule, changing/updating schedule, assigning teacher loading, viewing/printing teacher loading, viewing/printing subject’s schedule and printing/viewing of enrollment summary. The results are shown in Table 7.

Table 7. *Degree of Functionality of the Admission Monitoring Management System as perceived by the Manager Module*

FUNCTIONALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM	ADMISSION	MONITORING	Cebu		Consolacion		Cagayan de Oro		Mean	Vd
			X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd		
Center Manager										
1.	Viewing Registration Form for payment		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
2.	Viewing/Students Record		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
3.	Viewing Previous/old matriculation payment needed for current enrollment		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
4.	Viewing/Printing Schedule		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
5.	Viewing Teachers Loading		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
6.	Viewing/Subjects Schedule		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
7.	Viewing Registration Form for payment		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
8.	Viewing/Students Record		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
9.	Viewing of Enrollment Summary		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
Total number students enrolled on each subjects			5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5.0	WD
Total number of enrolled students per course or strand (SHS)			5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5.0	WD
10.	Viewing of Master List		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
11.	Viewing SHS Strand Categorization		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
12.	Viewing College Course Categorization		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
Total Mean of Center Manager			5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
SUB MEAN			5.0							WD
Academics Head										
1.	Plotting of subject’s schedule.		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
2.	Viewing/Printing Schedule		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
3.	Changing/Updating Schedule		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
4.	Assigning teacher Loading		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
5.	Viewing/Printing Teacher Loading		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
6.	Viewing/Printing Subjects Schedule		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
7.	Printing/Viewing of Enrollment Summary		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
Total number students enrolled on each subjects			5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5.0	WD
Total number of enrolled students per course or strand (SHS)			5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5.0	WD
8.	Viewing/Printing of Master List		5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
Total Mean of Academics Head			5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
SUB MEAN			5.0							WD
TOTAL MEAN			5.0							WD

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Well Developed (WD), 3.40 – 4.19 Developed (D), 2.60 – 3.39 Partially Developed (PaD), 1.80 – 2.59 Poorly Developed (PoD) 1.00 – 1.79 Not Developed (ND)

Table 7 tells that the center managers unanimously perceived the Admission Monitoring Management System as well-developed system. This means that viewing registration form for payment,

viewing student's record, viewing previous/old matriculation payment needed for current enrollment, viewing/printing schedule, viewing teachers loading, viewing subjects schedule, viewing registration form for payment, viewing student's record, viewing of enrollment summary, viewing of masterlist, viewing SHS strand categorization and viewing College course categorization are well developed systems. All areas in the Managers agrees and accepted that the Admission Monitoring Management System functionality are well developed. All area has the highest acceptability and responded a well-developed Admission Monitoring Management System functionality because they are more oriented of the system by the researcher.

Table 7 tells that the Admission Monitoring Management System as well-developed system is unanimously perceived to be well developed by the academic managers of the three areas. Suggesting that the plotting of subject's schedule, viewing/printing schedule, changing/updating schedule, assigning teacher loading, viewing/printing teacher loading, viewing/printing subject's schedule and printing/viewing of enrollment summary are known to be well developed systems in Admission Monitoring Management System. All areas in the Academics agrees and accepted that the Admission Monitoring Management System functionality are well developed. All area has the highest acceptability and responded a well-developed Admission Monitoring Management System functionality because they are more oriented of the system by the researcher.

System Operator

User of the system that comprises of Cashier, Registrar and Course consultants who runs the Admission Monitoring Management System during the registration process. In general, a system operator is one who runs the day-to-day operation of a Admission Monitoring Management System according to area; Cebu, Consolation and Cagayan De Oro.

Cashier. This section explains the degree of functionality of the Admission Monitoring Management System as perceived by the Cashiers in the three areas. The cashiers are concerned with the following components in the said system: view/print registration payment, confirm registration payment and input previous/old matriculation payment needed for current enrollment.

Registrar. This section discusses the degree of functionality of the Admission Monitoring Management System as perceived by the Registrars in the three areas. Printing/viewing of enrollment summary; printing of master list, SHS strand categorization, and College course categorization; viewing previous subjects enrolled by the students in the semester; viewing added/changed/dropped subjects and printing/viewing of enrollment summary are the processes that the registrars are concerned about in the system shown in Table 8.

Course Consultants. This section shows the degree of functionality of the Admission Monitoring Management System as perceived by the Course Consultants in the three areas. In the system, course consultants input/view registration form for payment, input application form for new and old, input/view plotted subjects, view matriculation payment confirmed by the cashier, view/print study load, process ID for new/lost ID, update plotted schedule for changed/dropped/added subjects and view students' information record. The results are shown in Table 8.

Table 8. Degree of Functionality of the Admission Monitoring Management System as perceived by the System Operators Module

FUNCTIONALITY MANAGEMENT SYSTEM	ADMISSION		MONITORING		Cebu		Consolacion		Cagayan de Oro		Mean	Vd
	X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd				
Cashier												
1. View/Print Registration payment.	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
2. Confirm Registration Payment	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
3. Input Previous/old matriculation payment needed for current enrollment.	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
Total Mean of Cashier	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
SUB MEAN												
	5.0											WD
Registrar												
1. Printing /Viewing of Enrollment Summary	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
Total number students enrolled on each subjects	5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5.0	WD
Total number of enrolled students per course or strand (SHS)	5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5.0	WD
2. Printing of Master List	4.0	D	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	4.7	WD
3. Printing of SHS Strand Categorization	4.0	D	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	4.7	WD
4. Printing of College Course Categorization	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
5. Viewing Previous Subjects Enrolled by the students/Semester	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
6. Viewing Add/Change/ Drop subjects.	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
7. Printing /Viewing of Enrollment Summary	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD
Total number students enrolled on each subject	5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5	WD	5.0	WD
Total Mean of Registrar	4.7	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	4.9	WD
SUB MEAN												
	4.9											WD
Course Consultants												
1. Input/View Registration Form for payment.	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	4.0	D	4.0	D	4.0	D	4.7	WD
2. Input Application Form for New and Old.	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	4.0	D	4.0	D	4.0	D	4.7	WD
3. Input/View Plotted Subjects.	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	D	5.0	D	5.0	D	5.0	WD
4. View Matriculation Payment confirmed by the	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	4.0	D	4.0	D	4.0	D	4.7	WD
Cashier.												
5. View/Print Study Load.	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	D	5.0	D	5.0	D	5.0	WD
6. Process ID for New/Lost ID	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	4.0	D	4.0	D	4.0	D	4.7	WD
7. Update plotted Schedule for Change/ Dropped /Add	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	D	5.0	D	5.0	D	5.0	WD
Subjects												
8. View/Students Information Record.	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	5.0	D	5.0	D	5.0	D	5.0	WD
Total Mean of Course Consultant	5.0	WD	5.0	WD	4.5	WD	4.5	WD	4.5	WD	4.8	WD
SUB MEAN												
	4.8											WD
TOTAL MEAN												
	4.9											WD

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Well Developed (WD), 3.40 – 4.19 Developed (D), 2.60 – 3.39 Partially Developed (PaD), 1.80 – 2.59 Poorly Developed (PoD) 1.00 – 1.79 Not Developed (ND)

As shown in Table 8, the cashiers in the three areas unanimously believed that Admission Monitoring Management System is a well-developed system. It is implying that cashiers find viewing/printing of registration payment, confirming registration payment and inputting previous/old

matriculation payment needed for current enrollment as well-developed processes in the system. All areas in the Cashiers agrees and accepted that the Admission Monitoring Management System functionality are well developed. All area has the highest acceptability and responded a well- developed Admission Monitoring Management System functionality because they are more oriented of the system by the researcher.

Table 8 shows that the Admission Monitoring Management System of the three areas is generally perceived to be well developed system by the cashiers. It means that the cashiers find the processes mentioned above to be efficient. But in particular, Cebu area’s cashier find the printing of the master list and SHS strand categorization to be developed only, while these are well developed in other areas. All areas in the Registrars agree and accepted that the Admission Monitoring Management System functionality is well developed. All area has the highest acceptability and responded a well-developed Admission Monitoring Management System functionality because they are more oriented of the system by the researcher.

Table 8 shows that the Admission Monitoring Management System of the three areas is generally perceived by the course consultants as well-developed system. They believed that inputting/viewing registration form for payment, inputting application form for new and old, inputting/viewing plotted subjects, viewing matriculation payment confirmed by the cashier, viewing/printing study load, processing ID for new/lost ID, updating plotted schedule for changed/dropped/added subjects and viewing students’ information record is well established in the system. All areas in the Course Consultants agrees and accepted that the Admission Monitoring Management System functionality are well developed. All area has the highest acceptability and responded a well-developed Admission Monitoring Management System functionality because they are more oriented of the system by the researcher. Summary of data on Admission Monitoring Management System according to respondents group role to the degree of functionality shown on Table 9.

Table 9. *Summary Table as to Admission Monitoring Management System according to respondents group role to the degree of functionality*

FUNCTIONALITY OF ADMISSION MONITORING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM ACCORDING TO ROLE		Vd
Administrator	4.9	WD
Manger	5.0	WD
System Operator	4.9	WD
Overall Total	4.93	WD

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Well Developed (WD), 3.40 – 4.19 Developed (D), 2.60 – 3.39 Partially Developed (PaD), 1.80 – 2.59 Poorly Developed (PoD), 1.00 – 1.79 Not Developed (ND)

As shown in table 9, the three areas as to Administrator, Manger and System Operator unanimously believed the functionality of the Admission Monitoring Management system is highly appreciated by the users with the total mean of 4.9, 5.0 and 4.9 respectively with the overall total mean of 4.93 percent as Well Developed management monitoring system.

Acceptability of Admission Monitoring Management System

An information systems theory that models how users come to accept and use a technology. The model suggests that when users are presented with a new technology, a number of factors influence their

decision about how and when they will use it, notably (Davis 1989):. increasing interest in end users' reactions to the Technology introduce by the researchers and to validate the importance of theories that predict and explain the Admission Monitoring Management Systems' acceptance and use (Davis 1989).

Perceived Usefulness

One of the independent constructs in the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). It is “the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would improve his/her job performance”. (Davis, 1989 AU95: The citation; Davis, 1989; matches multiple references). This portion presents the table which describes the perceived of usefulness of the Admission Monitoring Management System of Informatics College, Region VII as shown in Table 10.

Table 10. *The Perceived Usefulness of the Admission Monitoring Management System*

The degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance (Davis, 1989)	Cebu							Average	Consolacion							Average	Cagayan De Oro							Average	Mean	
	Adminstrator		Manager		System Operator				Adminstrator		Manager		System Operator				Adminstrator		Manager		System Operator					
	X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd	A		X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd	A		X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd	X			Vd
1. Using the AMMS it saves me time.	5	SA	5	SA	4	A	4.7	5	SA	5	SA	4	A	4.7	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	4.8
2. The AMMS supports critical aspects of my job.	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	5.0		
3. The AMMS enables me to accomplish tasks more quickly.	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	5.0		
4. Using the AMMS it allows me to accomplish more work than would otherwise be possible.	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	5.0		

5. Using the AMMS reduces the time I spend on unproductive activities.	5	S	A	4	A	5	S	A	4.7	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	4.9
6. Using the AMMS enhances my effectiveness on the job.	5	S	A	5	SA	4	A	4.7	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	5	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	4.9
7. Using the AMMS improves the quality of the work I do.	5	S	A	5	SA	4	A	4.7	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	5	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	4.9
8. Using the AMMS increase my productivity.	5	S	A	5	SA	5	S	A	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	5	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0
9. Using the AMMS make it easier to do my job.	5	S	A	5	SA	5	S	A	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	5	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0
10. Overall, I find the AMMS useful in my job.	5	S	A	5	SA	5	S	A	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	5	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0
Average	5.0	SA	4.9	SA	4.7	SA	4.9	5.0	5.0	SA	5.0	SA	4.9	SA	5.0	5.0	5.0	SA	5.0	SA	5.0	SA	5.0	4.95
Description	Strong Agree						4.9	Strong Agree						5.0	Strong Agree						5.0			
SUB X	4.96																							SA

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Strongly Agree (SA), 1.00 – 1.79 Strongly Disagree (SD), 3.40 – 4.19 Agree (A), 2.60 – 3.39 Neither Agree nor Disagree (NAD), 1.80 – 2.59 Disagree (D)

Table 10 shows that in general the administrators, managers and system operators strongly agree that the Admission Monitoring Management System is very useful in the college. It means that Admission Monitoring Management System is very useful in their everyday work as to; it saves time of the user, enables the user to accomplish tasks more quickly, reduces the time the user spends on unproductive activities and increase the user's productivity. Even though the system in the three areas are found to be useful, but in particular, the table reveals that Cebu area has the least mean score among the three. Specifically, system operators rated the least among respondents in Cebu area. Cebu area reveals the least mean score among the three as to two departments in Cebu area is doubtful the system will be implemented in the college.

Perceived Ease of Use

A component of Davis' (1989) original TAM model measured through ten self-report questionnaire items defined as "the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free of effort" (p. 320). This portion presents the table which describes the perceived ease of use of the Admission Monitoring Management System of Informatics College, Region VII as shown in Table 11.

Table 11. *The Perceived Ease of Use of the Admission Monitoring Management System*

The degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance (Davis, 1989)	Cebu						Average	Consolacion						Average	Cagayan De Oro						Average	Mean	
	Adminstrator		Manager		System Operator			Adminstrator		Manager		System Operator			Adminstrator		Manager		System Operator				
	X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd		X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd		X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd			
1. It is easy to use.	4	A	5	SA	4	A	4.3	5	SA	5	SA	4	A	4.7	5	SA	5	SA	4	A	4.7	4.6	
2. It is simple to use.	5	S	A	5	SA	5	S	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	4	A	4.7	5	SA	5	SA	4	A	4.7	4.8
3. It is user friendly.	4	A	5	SA	5	A	4.7	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	4	A	4.7	4.6	
4. It requires the fewest steps possible to accomplish what I want to do with it.	5	S	A	5	SA	5	S	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	4	A	5	SA	4	A	4.3	4.7
5. I can use it without written instructions.	5	S	A	5	SA	5	S	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	4	A	4.7	4	A	5	SA	5	SA	4.7	4.8
6. I can recover from mistakes quickly and easily.	5	S	A	5	SA	5	S	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	4	A	4.7	4	A	5	SA	4	A	4.3	4.7
7. Using it is effortless.	5	S	A	5	SA	4	A	4.7	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	4	A	5	SA	5	SA	4.7	4.8
8. I would find the system to be flexible to interact	5	S	A	5	SA	5	S	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5.0

with.																									
9. I would find the system to be flexible to interact with.	5	S	A	5	SA	5	S	A	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	4	A	4.7	4.9	
10. Overall, I find the AMMS easy to use.	5	S	A	5	SA	4	A	4.7	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	4.9		
	4.8	S	A	5.0	SA	4.7	S	A	4.8	5.0	SA	5.0	SA	4.6	SA	4.9	4.6	SA	5.0	SA	4.4	SA	4.7	4.8	
Description	Strong Agree							4.8	Strong Agree							4.9	Strong Agree							4.7	
SUB X																								4.8	SA

Table 11 shows that in general the administrators, managers and system operators strongly agree that the Admission Monitoring Management System is very easy to use. It means that all the area accepts that the Admission Monitoring Management System is easy to use in their every day job as to; simple to use, It requires fewest steps possible to accomplish the job, they can recover from mistakes quickly and easily, they would find the system to be flexible to interact with and they would find the system to be flexible to interact. Even though using the system in the three areas are found to be easy, but in particular, the table says that Cagayan de Oro area has the least mean score among the three. Specifically, system operators rated the least among respondents in Cagayan de Oro area. Cagayan De Oro has the least mean score because some of the respondents are on probationary status.

Attitude towards using

The system has a strong positive direct effect on Admission Monitoring Management System acceptance. And “the degree of evaluative affect that an individual associates *with using* the Admission Monitoring Management System in his/her job. Linking attitude directly to Information Technology acceptance has been found to be significant in several studies (Algahtani & King, 1998; Davis, 1993; Guimaraes & Igbaria, 1997; Igbaria, 1993). This portion presents the table which describes the attitude towards using the Admission Monitoring Management System of Informatics College, Region VII as shown in Table 12.

Table 12. *The Perceived Attitude Towards Using the Admission Monitoring Management System*

The degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would	Cebu						Average	Consolacion						Average	Cagayan De Oro						Average	Mean					
	Adminstrator		Manager		System Operator			Adminstrator		Manager		System Operator			Adminstrator		Manager		System Operator								
	X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd		X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd		X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd							
	X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd	

10. Overall, I find the AMMS is good to use	5	S	A	5	SA	5	S	A	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5.0
	4.9	S	A	4.9	SA	4.9	S	A	4.9	4.3	SA	4.5	SA	4.3	SA	4.4	4.5	SA	4.9	SA	4.3	SA	4.6	4.6
Description	Strong Agree						4.9	Strong Agree						4.4	Strong Agree						4.6			
SUB X	4.6																						SA	

Table 12 shows that in general the administrators, managers and system operators have high positive attitude towards using the Admission Monitoring Management System. It means that all the area has the attitude to use the Admission Monitoring Management System the leads to its acceptability. Even though the three areas have high positive attitude towards the system, but in particular, the results shows that the Consolacion area has the least mean score among the three. Specifically, the system operators gave the least rate among respondents in Consolacion area. Consolacion has the least mean score among them because they are doubtful and hesitant that the Admission Monitoring Management System will be implemented in the college.

Behavioral Intention

The original TAM model (Davis, 1986) indicates that behavioral intention exerts a positive effect on usage. Bagozzi et al. (1992), Szajna (1996) and Morris et al. (1997) found that behavioral intention might influence usage. It is the common factor being employed by all technology acceptance theories. It aims to define individuals' act in use a particular technology. This portion presents the table which describes the behavioral intension to use the Admission Monitoring Management System of Informatics College, Region VII as shown in Table 13.

Table 13. *The Perceived Behavioral Intention of Using the Admission Monitoring Management System*

The degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would enhance his or her job performance (Davis, 1989)	Cebu						Average	Consolacion						Average	Cagayan De Oro						Average	Mean		
	Adminstrator		Manag er		System Operator			Adminstrator		Manager		System Operator			Adminstra-tor		Manager		System Operator					
	X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd		X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd		X	Vd	X	Vd	X	Vd				
1. This AMMS has all the functions and capabilities I	5	SA	5	SA	5	S	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5.0

expect it to have																							
2. The organization of information on the system screens is clear.	5	SA	5	SA	5	S	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5.0	
3. The interface of this AMMS is pleasant.	5	SA	5	SA	5	S	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	3	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5.0	
4. The information (such as system help, on-screen messages, and other documentation) provided with this system is clear.	5	SA	5	SA	5	S	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5.0	
5. This AMMS has all the functions and capabilities I expect it to have	5	SA	5	SA	5	S	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5.0	
6. I am able to complete my work/admission quickly using this AMMS.	5	SA	5	SA	4	A	4.7	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	4.9	
7. I am able to efficiently complete my work/admission using this AMMS.	5	SA	5	SA	4	A	4.7	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	4.9	

8. It was easy to learn to use this AMMS.	5	SA	5	SA	5	S	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5.0	
9. Overall, I am satisfied with how easy it is to use this AMMS	5	SA	5	SA	4	A	4.7	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	4.9	
10. Overall, I am satisfied with this AMMS and I am willing to use the system for my work.	5	SA	5	SA	4	A	4.7	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	5	SA	5	SA	5	SA	5.0	4.9	
5.0	SA	5.0	SA	4.6	S	4.9	5.0	SA	5.0	SA	5.0	SA	5.0	5.0	SA	5.0	SA	5.0	SA	5.0	5.0		
Description	Strong Agree				4.9	Strong Agree				5.0	Strong Agree				5.0	Strong Agree				5.0			
SUB X	5.0																						SA

Table 13 shows that in general the administrators, managers and system operators have high behavioral intention of using the Admission Monitoring Management System. It means that behavioral intension of all the area to accept the Admission Monitoring Management System is highly appreciated since based from the survey they want a new Admission System that would really help the college during the admission process. Even though the three areas have high behavioral intention of using the system, but in particular, the results shows that Cebu area has the least mean score among the three. Specifically, the system operators in Cebu gave the least rate among respondents. Cebu has the least mean score among them because they are doubtful and hesitant that the Admission Monitoring Management System will be implemented in the college.

Summary of data on the Acceptability of Admission Monitoring Management System as to Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Attitude towards using and Behavioral Intention to use as Technology Acceptance Model Variables shown on Table 14.

Table 14. *Summary Table as to Technology Acceptance Model Variables*

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) Variables Venkatesh and Davis (2000)	Cebu		Consolacion		Cagayan De Oro		Mean
	X	Vb	X	Vb	X	Vb	
Perceived Usefulness	4.9	SA	5.0	SA	5.0	SA	5.0
Perceived Ease of Use	4.8	SA	4.9	SA	4.7	SA	4.8
Attitude Towards Using	4.9	SA	4.4	SA	4.6	SA	4.6
Behavioral Intention to Use	4.9	SA	5.0	SA	5.0	SA	5.0

Mean	4.9	SA	4.8	SA	4.8	SA	4.8
Overall Description	Strongly Agree						4.8

Legend: 4.20 – 5.00 Strongly Agree (SA), 3.40 – 4.19 Agree (A), 2.60 – 3.39 Neither Agree nor Disagree (NAD), 1.80 – 2.59 Disagree (D), 1.00 – 1.79 Strongly Disagree (SD)

In Table 14, it shows that the administrators, managers and system operators in the three areas have high positive perception on usefulness and ease of use, high positive attitude and behavioral intention in using the system. It means that Technology Acceptance Model is validated through the acceptance of the three areas by using the Admission Monitoring Management System. Among the three areas, Cebu has the highest mean scores, while Consolacion and Cagayan de Oro receives the same mean score. All areas has a high and positive attitude towards using the system since the proposed Admission Monitoring Management Systems answers the following needs as to; Security of Data, Easy transaction from student registration to releasing of students master listing and a centralized database management system. The technology acceptance model proposes that perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness predict the acceptance of information technology. Since its inception, the model has been tested with various applications in tens of studies and has become the most widely applied model of user acceptance and usage. Nevertheless, the reported findings on the model are mixed in terms of statistical significance, direction, and magnitude. In this study, we conducted a meta-analysis based on 3 selected empirical areas in order to synthesize the empirical evidence. The results suggest that both the correlation between usefulness and acceptance, and that between usefulness and ease of use are somewhat strong. And the relationship between ease of use and acceptance is also strong, and its significance does pass and accepted as Strongly Agree. According to (Paul Legris, JohnInghamb and Pierre Collette, 2003), Information systems (IS) implementation is costly and has a relatively low success rate. Since the seventies, IS research has contributed to a better understanding of this process and its outcomes. The early efforts concentrated on the identification of factors that facilitated IS use. This produced a long list of items that proved to be of little practical value. It became obvious that, for practical reasons, the factors had to be grouped into a model in a way that would facilitate analysis of IS use. They conclude that TAM is a useful model but has to be integrated into a broader one which would include variables related to both human and social change processes, and to the acceptance of the innovation model.

Concordance Agreement

To test the development of Admission Monitoring Management System and the acceptability if TAM' construct, the Kendall's W (also known as Kendall's coefficient of concordance) is being used thru XLSTAT Pearson Edition an add-on for Microsoft Excel. Kendall's W ranges from 0 (no agreement) to 1 (complete agreement). If the test statistic W is 1, then all the survey respondents have been unanimous, and each respondent has assigned the same order to the list of concerns. If W is 0, then there is no overall trend of agreement among the respondents, and their responses may be regarded as essentially random. Intermediate values of W indicate a greater or lesser degree of unanimity among the various responses. Kendall's W makes no assumptions regarding the nature of the probability distribution and can handle any number of distinct outcomes. W is linearly related to the mean value of the Spearman's rank correlation coefficients between all pairs of the rankings over which it is calculated. Between the AMMS and TAM's construct, the computed *W* of 0.600 of the four areas and the computed *W* of 0.600 on the four Technology model with an Average of 7.5 value. As shown on Table 15.

Table 15. Concordance agreement established among four Technology Acceptance Model (Kendall's Coefficient of Concordance (*W*))

AREA	Perceived Usefulness	Perceived Ease of Use	Attitude Towards Using	Behavioral Intention to Use	TOTAL	
Cebu	2	4	2	2	10	
Consolacion	1.5	3	4	1.5	10	
Cagayan de Oro	1.5	4	3	1.5	10	
Mean	5	11	9	5		
<i>k</i>	4					
<i>m</i>	3					
<i>W</i>	0.6000					
<i>r</i>	0.4000					
χ^2	5.4000					
<i>df</i>	3					
<i>p-value</i>	0.1447					
	0.6					
Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) Variables	Cebu	Consolacion	Cagayan de Oro	Sum of Ranks	Difference	D ²
Perceived Usefulness	2	1.5	1.5	5	-2.5	6.25
Perceived Ease of Use	4	3	4	11	3.5	12.25
Attitude Towards Using	2	4	3	9	1.5	2.25
Behavioral Intention to Use	2	1.5	1.5	5	-2.5	6.25
Average				7.5		27
<i>N</i>	4					
<i>M</i>	3					
<i>W</i>	0.600					
<i>r</i>	0.400					
χ^2 stat	5.400					
χ^2 critical	7.815					
<i>df</i>	3					
<i>p-value</i>	0.1447					

In Table 15, The coefficient of concordance result revealed that there is a moderate agreement among the four technology acceptance model variables with moderate positive non-significant relationship. It further shows that AMMS is accepted.

Summary

This study was conducted at Informatics College Region VII, Cebu, Consolacion and Cagayan De Oro respectively. It aimed to develop, accepts and validates the Technology Management Admission Monitoring Management System; that the data will be reduced as record keeping will be done more efficiently, as adding, deleting and updating information will reduce the use of stationary- by reducing cost-

as well as be less time-consuming. This will lead Informatics College to become more productive as employees could perform additional tasks, Data entered will not be redundant as the Information System will utilize the “Repetition”, Overheads will be drastically reduced. This will result in a reduction of office space and equipment. This will maximize Informatics College profits, The data entered will be confidential and secure, via the use of passwords, Data could be accessed by multiple employees at a time. This will lead to Informatics College becoming more productive and to become a competitive in the Information and Communication Technology.

This study used a descriptive method of research wherein unstructured questionnaire was the instrument used in data gathering using the Technology Acceptance Model (Davis, 1986). The proposed Technology Management Admission Monitoring Management System for Informatics College Region VII has the following elements that were used in developing the Admission Monitoring Management System, which are: 1. Peopleware, is the person profile involved in the development of the system 2. Dataware, which contains the information of the respondents and the degree functionality of group roles as to; Administrator, Managers and System Operators. And the acceptability of Admission Monitoring Management System as Technology Acceptance Model use motivation 3. Software, which was used in the development of the Admission Monitoring Management System. The software that was used in developing the Admission Monitoring Management System was NodeJS: a cross-platform JavaScript runtime environment for servers and applications. It is built on a single-threaded, non-blocking event loop, the Google Chrome V8 JavaScript engine, and a low-level I/O API for the frontend and MySQL: an open source relational database management system (Relational Database Management System) based on Structured Query Language (SQL) and runs on virtually all platforms, including Linux, UNIX, and Windows for the backend and GIT BASH command line shell.

This study utilized the descriptive-correlation method. It aimed to elicit the relationship between the developments of Admission Monitoring Management System and TAM’s construct acceptability. Based on the statistical analysis and computations made, the following were the findings:

Findings

Based on the gender representation majority of personnel are dominated by Female when it comes to the work force since mostly are assigned on the marketing personnel and the school President prefers female as the top managers of the school. Research has established a mixed picture for contemporary female leadership. Women leaders on average manifest valued, effective leadership styles, even somewhat more than men do, and are often associated with successful business organizations (Alice H. Eagly ,2007).

The age of the respondents ranges from 20 to 60 years old, and most of them are in the middle age group that is, within the age bracket of 30 to 40 years old. Most of them are on the middle group age since the Manager of each Center prefers this age bracket. Surprisingly, there are only two (2) of them who are in the old age group (that is, within the age bracket 50 to 60 years old). Two of the employees are in the old age group because these two are the Heads of their own department. But the majority respondents at the age bracket of 30 yrs. old to 40yrs. old especially who has a responsibility in the institution. This implies that among the characteristics attributed to Xers life, the following appear most often. They aspire more than previous generations to achieve a balance between work and life they are more independent, autonomous and self-reliant than previous generations. They value continuous learning and skill development. They have strong technical skills, are results focused, and are “ruled by a sense of accomplishment and not the clock. Xers naturally question authority figures and are not intimidated by them. They can tolerate work as long as it is fun Although they are individualistic, they may also like teamwork, more so than boomers (Anick Tolbize, 2008). While Position, shows that most of the respondents, roughly 41.9 percent of them, are course consultants. It implies that the driving force of academe is concentrated in the course consultant

positions. The course consultants as the driving force the college since they are the life and blood of the college by bringing more students to enroll in the said college. The other positions are only taking a small part of the college considering that these positions are either administrative or support service in nature. It is also important to note that the positions are also evenly spread among the three areas. The position of the respondents was equally distributed by the three areas as to Cebu, Consolacion and Cagayan De Oro and it implies that the Information Technology organization of the institution is ideal and will distributed and therefore the organization is systematic and organized. The Department, has approximately 41.94 percent of the respondents are working in the Marketing department, around 29.03 percent of them are in Staff department, roughly 19.35 percent of them are working as administrators, and only about 9.68 percent of them are in Technical department. Most of the respondents are working in the Marketing Department since they have the most personnel in the area and as mandated by the president of the institution that they are the most vital part of the department because it measure the institution's entrepreneurial orientation. The accountability and innovativeness of the marketing department represent the two major drivers of its influence. A marketing department's influence is related positively to market orientation, which in turn is related positively to firm performance. It also suggests a dual relationship between the marketing department's influence and market orientation. A key implication is that marketers should become more accountable and innovative to gain more influence (Peter C. Verhoef, Peter S.H. Leeflang, 2009). Employee Status implies that the institution values its employees and builds better relationship. The data also shows that the company did not practice the ENDO End of Contract policy which is more common in the Philippines industry. Contractual employees' morale and human resource management are affected by the "end of contract" policy in the country. Emotions, attitude, satisfaction, and outlook that comprises employee morale; and hiring, training and development, and compensation and benefits operations of the human resource, effects are presumed (Angelica L. Ditché and Hazel Joy A. Miranda, 2017).

The Functionality of Admission Monitoring Management System according to; Administrator Module implication of the functionality of the Admission Monitoring Management system to the Administrator and Service officer module is highly appreciated by the users with the total mean of 4.9 as Well Developed Management System. Manager Module implication of the functionality of the Admission Monitoring Management system to the Manager and Academics Head module is highly appreciated by the users with the total mean of 5.0 as Well Developed Management System. System Operators Module implication of the functionality of the Admission Monitoring Management system to the Cashier, Registrar and Course Consultant module is highly appreciated by the users with the total mean of 4.9 as Well Developed Management System.

Acceptability of Admission Monitoring Management system shows that the administrators, managers and system operators in the three areas have high positive perception on usefulness and ease of use, high positive attitude and behavioral intention in using the system. It means that Technology Acceptance Model is validated through the acceptance of the three areas by using the Admission Monitoring Management System. Among the three areas, Cebu has the highest mean scores, while Consolacion and Cagayan de Oro receives the same mean score. All areas have a high and positive attitude towards using the system since the proposed Admission Monitoring Management Systems answers the following needs as to; Security of Data, Easy transaction from student registration to releasing of students master listing and a centralized database management system.

The technology acceptance model proposes that perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness predict the acceptance of information technology. Since its inception, the model has been tested with various applications in tens of studies and has become the most widely applied model of user acceptance and usage. Nevertheless, the reported findings on the model are mixed in terms of statistical significance, direction, and magnitude. In this study, we conducted a meta-analysis based on 3 selected empirical areas in order to

synthesize the empirical evidence. The results suggest that both the correlation between usefulness and acceptance, and that between usefulness and ease of use are somewhat strong. And the relationship between ease of use and acceptance is also strong, and its significance does pass and accepted as Strongly Agree.

According to (Paul Legris, JohnInghamb and Pierre Collette, 2003), Information systems (IS) implementation is costly and has a relatively low success rate. Since the seventies, IS research has contributed to a better understanding of this process and its outcomes. The early efforts concentrated on the identification of factors that facilitated IS use. This produced a long list of items that proved to be of little practical value. It became obvious that, for practical reasons, the factors had to be grouped into a model in a way that would facilitate analysis of IS use. They conclude that TAM is a useful model but has to be integrated into a broader one which would include variables related to both human and social change processes, and to the acceptance of the innovation model.

In the concordance agreement established among the aforementioned variables show that there is a moderate agreement among the four technology acceptance model variables with moderate positive non-significant relationship among the aforementioned variables.

CONCLUSION

Based on the result of the Admission Monitoring Management System for Informatics College Region VII in terms of Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Attitude Towards Using and Behavioral Intention to Use the Technology Management Program should be given immediate attention and action by the college. The Admission Monitoring Management System as the degree of functionality was evaluated and rated Well Developed with a weighted mean of 4.93 percent in general in term as to; Administrator Module, Managers Module and System Operators Module. The Admission Monitoring Management System as the degree of acceptability was evaluated and rated Strongly Agree with a weighted mean of 4.8 percent in general in term as to; Administrator: Technical Personnel, Service Officers, Managers: Center Manager, Academics Head and System Operators: Cashier, Course Consultant and Registrar.

Recommendations

Anchored on the conclusion of the study, it is highly recommended that the Admission Monitoring Management System with its User's Manual should be implemented, accepted and it must be sustained in Informatics College, Region VII in order to enhance and strengthen the Admission Monitoring of students in the institutions. The following are recommended for corrective actions in addressing possible weakness of the study: The proposed admission monitoring management system should be enhanced further to fit suit the user's needs. It is necessary that the Managers and System Operators personnel in charge should be computer literate else they will undergo Computer Application Training. Administrator of the system must be knowledgeable enough in computer networking management and computer system servicing to maintain the admission monitoring management system. Administrators must have the ability to organize and apply the existing monitoring management system. It is strongly recommended that Cebu, Consolacion and Cagayan De Oro must have an accurate network infrastructure for the Admission Monitoring Management System to run properly. Future researchers are encouraged to conduct similar in-depth studies in line with the needs of the changing time.

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